

New Directions in Research & Innovation – A Case of a Private University

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Abstract:

This case study about research and innovation strategy of an upcoming private university started recently. Even though it is new university, it has rich experience in higher education training service of about 30 years. Being worked as affiliated group of colleges, it has developed the abilities to innovate but due to lack of autonomy it could not implement its innovative ideas. Now being an autonomous university with intentions to innovate both in academic activities and research related programmes, Srinivas university could able to establish itself as a potential university for research and innovations. In this paper we have discussed the saga of success of Srinivas Group of institutions into Srinivas university, the leadership abilities for future innovations and the strategies followed to realize its objectives by making decisions in implementing effective steps and new directions in research and innovations.

Keywords : New directions in research, Autonomy in HEI, Research & Innovations.

1. INTRODUCTION :

Srinivas University has an objective of developing itself as Research and Skill focused university. Along with UG courses which are skill focused and PG courses which are skill and research focused, the university has started many research focused courses in the campus. These include M.Phil., M.Tech. (by Research), M.S. (by Research), Ph.D. (Regular & Part-Time), D.Sc., D.Litt., Post-Graduate Research Certificate, and Post-Doctoral Research Certificate courses. These research courses are offered on campus based research and scholarly publications in Conference proceedings and peer reviewed indexed Journals.

The University offers academic programmes at UG and PG levels which are developed and monitored by Board of Studies (BOS), Academic Council, and Board of Management of the university with the final approvals from Board of Governors of the University. The research courses are developed and monitored by Research & Innovation Council, and Board of Management, with the final approval from Board of Governors of the University.

2. SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY – JOURNEY SO FAR :

Srinivas University, Mangalore, is a Private Research & Skill focussed University in Mangalore, Karnataka, India established in 2013 by Karnataka State Act. Srinivas University is the flagship of 18 Srinivas Group of Institutions started by A. Shama Rao Foundation, Mangalore, India, a private Charitable Trust founded in 1988 by an Eminent Chartered Accountant A. Raghavendra Rao. A. Shama Rao Foundation has started many professional colleges in Mangalore which include Srinivas Institute of Medical Sciences and Research Center, Srinivas Institute of Dental Sciences, Srinivas Institute of Technology, Srinivas College of Pharmacy, Srinivas Institute of Nursing Sciences, A Shama Rao Nursing School, Srinivas Integrated Campus, Srinivas College of Hotel Management, Vijayalakshmi Institute of Hospitality Sciences, Srinivas First Grade College, Srinivas School of Engineering, Srinivas Institute of Management Studies, Srinivas College of Physiotherapy, Srinivas School of Business, Srinivas School of Management, Srinivas College of Education, Srinivas Institute of Social Work. Srinivas University started functioning from May 2015 with MCA course.

Presently, Srinivas University offers undergraduate, postgraduate, and research courses under 9 Faculties/Colleges with about 75 courses. The University made innovations in designing and starting new super specialty programmes both in UG, and PG level as per present and future industry relevance, innovations in examination system through a focus on continuous evaluation and to make it foolproof. The University has established networking with many industries, universities, and Education service providers to substantially improve the quality and weightage of the courses and degrees respectively. Presently Srinivas University has Eight Colleges offering innovative industry oriented specialized courses of UG, PG, and Research levels. The nine Colleges functioning under Srinivas university are :

- (1) College of Business Management & Commerce
- (2) College of Computer & Information Sciences
- (3) College of Social Sciences & Humanities
- (4) College of Engineering & Technology
- (5) College of Hotel Management & Tourism
- (6) College of Physiotherapy
- (7) College of Allied Health Sciences
- (8) College of Education
- (9) College of Design

Challenges Faced :

- (1) Brand Creation
- (2) Creating Awareness
- (3) Attracting Research Projects :
- (4) Research orientation

3. PROFESSIONAL BACKGROUND AND EXPERIENCE OF THE LEADER :

Shri. CA. A. Raghavendra Rao, Founder Chancellor of Srinivas University has established the A. Shama Rao Foundation to achieve his stated aim of transforming society through quality education which will be in harmony with the social, economic and ecological environment. This firm belief was the driving force which created the Srinivas Group of Colleges under the umbrella of A. Shama Rao Foundation. Shri. CA A. Raghavendra Rao has a unique and focused approach towards life. He dons different hats in his service to the cause of ‘Nation Building’. He is successful Chartered Accountant with offices in Seven cities across India, he is a hotelier par excellence who has created one of the first and finest 3 –Star hotel with a vegetarian restaurant as its hallmark. His most notable contribution has been in

moulding the careers of thousands of students through a chain of colleges imparting professional education in such varied fields as Engineering, Medicine, Physiotherapy, Hotel Management, Business Management, Computer application, Nursing and Pharmacy. His dedication and excellence in his field makes him a completely reliable person and hence he has set an example to his clients, staff, students and admirers.

EARLY LIFE

Shri. A. Raghavendra Rao was born in Benagal, Pejamangore Village, Udupi on 16th October 1937 to Late Shri. A. Shama Rao, (Retd. Headmaster, BEM Higher Secondary P.U College, Car Street, Mangalore) and Smt. A. Indiramma. He completed his elementary education in SVS Elementary School, Innanje and then joined the SVH High School. He completed his intermediate examinations as well as graduation in Commerce at the M.G.M. College in Udupi and came to Mangalore to pursue his higher education in Chartered Accountancy. In the year 1965, he set up his independent practice as a Chartered Accountant at Felix Pai Bazar, Mangalore.

CAREER

Having started his practice with a single staff in his office, today there are 75 employees working under the CA firm M/s Raghavendra Rao Chartered Accountants, Mangalore and has offices at seven cities spread across the country. Today he is universally acknowledged as one of the senior most professionals amongst the fraternity of Chartered Accountants. In 1979, he contested for the South India Regional Council (S.I.R.C) of Institute of Chartered Accountants in Chennai and won the election. During his four-year tenure, he served as the Chairman of the India regional Chartered Accountant Students Association at Chennai and also as Secretary of S.I.R.C for some time. During this time, he was the taxation committee Chairman of the S.I.R.C and conducted regional taxation seminars at Mangalore. Not one to rest on his laurels, his innate talent as an entrepreneur saw him enter the hospitality industry with “Hotel Srinivas” in 1980. The Hotel has the unique distinction of being one of the first hotels to be classified as a 3-Star hotel despite the fact that it had a multi-cuisine vegetarian restaurant while the trend internationally was to attach a Non-Vegetarian restaurant to any star category hotel.

In the year 1988, he set up the “A. Shama Rao Foundation” a trust dedicated to advancement of his belief that “Education is the prime driver in transforming Society”. He found strong support for his vision from the then Vice-Chancellor of Mangalore University, Prof. Shafiullah under whose able guidance and encouragement Shri. A. Raghavendra Rao set up the first professional degree college under the aegis of A. Shama Rao Foundation, Mangalore. The college named “Srinivas College of Hotel Management” offered a 3-year Bachelor’s Degree in Hotel Management. From modest beginnings, the college, as well as the foundation, has grown many times over. Today the sixteen colleges of the foundation offer more than 78 programmes in various fields of study.

PROFESSIONAL QUALIFICATION:

- Articleship of Chartered Accountancy course under Late Sri A. Umanath Rao, C.A., Mangalore.

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- Member of Institute of C.A of India in 1965 (A.C.A.) & Fellow of ICAI in 1970 (F.C.A.)

PROFESSIONAL ACHIEVEMENTS:

- Setup independent practice as Chartered Accountant at Felix Pai Bazar, Mangalore in March 1965.
- Senior Partner of M/s. A. Raghavendra Rao, Chartered Accountants, Mangalore and having Branches in 7 other cities in India.
- Member of the Southern Indian Regional Council of Chartered Accountants of India, Madras for the period Of 1979-83.
- Chairman of the SIRC C A Students Association, Madras in 1980-81.
- Secretary of SIRC, Madras in 1982-83.
- Leading consultant & Auditor for Finance, Trading Commercial & Industrial concerns.

CONTRIBUTION TO SOCIETY

- CA A. Raghavendra Rao has helped quite a lot in enhancing the life of many students. His belief that nobody should be denied an opportunity to learn has seen many so called below average students evolve in to world class professionals in their chosen field. But for his vision, many of them would have withered away into life of oblivion. He also believes that success comes to those who are disciplined in life and focused on their goals. His institutions have always laid great stress on disciplined life both inside and outside the campus.
- He launched a special insurance scheme in association with National Insurance Company, named “Srinivas Arogya Card”. This scheme makes it easy for poor and downtrodden to have access to modern medical care at “Srinivas Hospital” without any cost to the families living below poverty line. The scheme is supported by the Karnataka government and it has thousands of members.
- The A. Shama Rao Foundation every year honours notable contributions in the following fields:
- A Shama Rao Memorial Outstanding Teacher Award from 2009 is conferred on a teacher from undivided Dakshina Kannada district who has rendered outstanding service in promoting and popularizing education in high schools or at pre-university college level.
- A Shama Rao Foundation award for the outstanding contribution to the development of Dakshina Kannada district from 2010 this award is conferred on a person who has rendered yeoman service in the development of the undivided Dakshina Kannada district.
- A Shama Rao Foundation award for outstanding social worker of Dakshina Kannada district from 2010 this award is conferred on a person who has helped to uplift the life of the citizens either through social work or as a public servant in the undivided Dakshina Kannada district

The vision and mission of Srinivas university is concurrent with the personal vision and mission of its Chancellor who believes in educating and empowering youth to unleash the hidden potential to transform society.

4. OPPORTUNITIES IN THE CURRENT EDUCATION SECTOR FOR RESEARCH

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Recognized as a private research university, Srinivas university and its stakeholders got an opportunity to do innovations in both teaching-learning models and research models through maximum offered autonomy for Excellency. Srinivas University has decided to encash this opportunity of autonomy for innovation in research and contribution effectively and efficiently by using its 30 years of academic and research experience with responsibility and accountability. In the process of realizing its objectives to become a world recognized university in research and innovation, Srinivas university has already identified four core areas for intensive research, which include International Research Centre in ICCT (Information Communication and Computing Technology), International Research Centre in Nanotechnology, International Research Centre in Productivity and Innovations, and International Research Centre in Innovations in Higher Education & Research. Srinivas University also has started a new initiative called establishment of Atomic Research Centres which are individual faculty co-ordinated research centres in the form of a small team to plan and organize research on a small innovative and futuristic topic.

Private universities can become successful only if they focus on research in individual subjects/specified areas and multi-disciplinary areas. Investment in research is the primary to attract national and international students for admission. Private university faculties have more freedom to collaborate, seek for fund and start new programmes which have research components. By incorporating research content in UG and PG course curriculum, students can be utilized to get extra-ordinary research output. Private universities have opportunity to organize various seminars, workshops and conferences frequently to promote research in contemporary areas.

(a) Opportunities :

- Opportunity to focus on research by reserving substantial part of their funds on research and development which enhances the name, fame and admission □ Freedom to appoint faculty members who have research inclination & interest irrespective of vacancies in the department
- Opportunity to generate research fund through industry collaboration, public contribution and government agencies

(b) Challenges :

- Creating interest in research among faculties and students
- Attracting research funds from industry collaboration, public contribution and government agencies
- Enhancing research contribution in terms of publications, IPR, patents etc.
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5. VARIOUS INNOVATIVE RESEARCH PROGRAMMES :

Srinivas University though in its infant stage, dared to make fearless innovations in the field of research and development. The university has started many atomic research centre under each college and to fuel research and publications by faculty members supported to give seed money for micro-projects, organized many conferences for discussion on their research results, and started 4 international open accessible journals for free and quick publication of

research outcome. The university also started many research programmes to attract interested research scholars in various areas under its departments/colleges :

(1) Business management & commerce : College of Business management and commerce started M.Phil., Ph.D., D.Litt., Post-graduate Research Certificate in Management, Post-graduate Research Certificate in Commerce, Post-Doctorate Research Certificate in Management, and Post-Doctorate Research Certificate in Commerce. The eligibility and regulations of the research programmes are given in table 1.

(2) Computer & information sciences : College of Computer & information sciences started M.Phil., Ph.D., D.Sc., Post-graduate Research Certificate in Computer science, Post-graduate Research Certificate in Computer science, Post-graduate Research Certificate in Information Science, Post-Doctorate Research Certificate in Computer science, and Post-Doctorate Research Certificate in Information Science. The eligibility and regulations of the research programmes are given in table 1.

(3) Social sciences & humanities : College of Social sciences & humanities started M.Phil., Ph.D., D.Litt, Post-graduate Research Certificate in Social science, Post-graduate Research Certificate in Social science, and Post-Doctorate Research Certificate in Social Science. The eligibility and regulations of the research programmes are given in table 1.

(4) Hotel Management & Tourism : College of Hotel management & Tourism started M.Phil., Ph.D. programmes. The eligibility and regulations of the research programmes are given in table 1.

(5) Education : College of Education has started M.Phil., Ph.D. and D.Litt. programmes. The eligibility and regulations of the research programmes are given in table 1.

(6) Engineering & Technology : College of Engineering & Technology offers M.Tech. (by Research), M.S. (by Research), Ph.D., D.Sc., Post-graduate Research Certificate in different areas of engineering and technology, Post-graduate Research Certificate in different areas of engineering and technology, Post-Doctorate Research Certificate in different areas of engineering and technology. The eligibility and regulations of the research programmes are given in table 1.

(7) Physiotherapy : College of Physiotherapy offers Ph.D. and D.Sc. programmes. The eligibility and regulations of the research programmes are given in table 1.

(8) Health Sciences : College of Allied Health Sciences also offers Ph.D. and D.Sc. programmes, and Post-Doctorate Research Certificates in different areas of health sciences. The eligibility and regulations of the research programmes are given in table 1.

6. INNOVATIVE METHODOLOGIES/TECHNOLOGIES DEPLOYED IN RESEARCH PROGRAMMES :

In order to realize the research objectives of the University by involving all stakeholders, the research and innovation council has developed some innovative methodologies to do research in Management, Social Sciences, Education, Engineering & Technology, and Health Sciences. This include (1) A new research framework called Company & NGO analysis for Business Management, Social sciences, and Education related research. (2) A new Research method named Patent Analysis in Engineering, technology, and health sciences. (3) A method of system / concept/ idea/ strategy analysis called ABCD analysis. (4) An organizational performance improvement model called Theory of Accountability. These four methodologies allow researchers to analyze the research problems in new qualitative perspective.

Srinivas university is also starting two future technology based research centres in emerging Universal General Purpose Technologies (UGPT) which include Information Communication

and Computation Technology (ICCT) and Nanotechnology (NT). In coming days Srinivas University focus on advanced cutting edge research in ICCT and NT by considering the underlying technologies of ICCT and NT as its flagship research programmes. It is planned to develop Srinivas Nanotechnology Research Centre and Srinivas ICCT Research Centre as International research centres to attract international projects funding and international researchers in near future.

7. DETAILS OF RESEARCH PROGRAMMES :

The admission for research programmes is open twice annually during January and July through an entrance exam. The eligibility for our research programmes is given in table 2 and the annual course fees as well as annual research performance for individual courses are given in table 3.

Table 2 : Eligibility for admission of Research courses of Srinivas University

S. No.	Research Course/Degree	Eligibility for Admission
1	M.Phil.	Masters degree in respective field with 55% marks
2	M.Tech. (By research)	B.Tech or Masters degree in related field with 60% marks
3	M.S. (By research)	B.Tech or Masters degree in related field with 60% marks
4	Ph.D.	Masters degree in respective field with 55% marks
5	D.Litt. / D.Sc.	Ph.D. degree in related subjects with minimum 5 years Post-Doctoral experience with at least 10 journal research publications after Ph.D. in related field as first author
6	Post-graduate Research Certificate	Working professional with Masters degree in respective field with 55% marks
7	Post-doctoral Research Certificate	Working professional with Ph.D. degree in respective field

Table 3 : Annual fee structure and total minimum publications required for Research Courses

S. No.	Research Course/Degree	Minimum Years of completion	Conference Publications Required	Scholarly Publications required in Journals	Annual Fees Structure (Rs.)
1	M.Phil.	One	2	1	60,000
2	M.Tech. (By research)	Two - Three	4	2	60,000
3	M.S. (By research)	Two-Three	4	2	60,000
4	Ph.D.	Three-Four	6	4+	60,000
5	D.Litt. / D.Sc.	Five years after Ph.D.	6	10+	90,000
6	Post-graduate Research Certificate	One-Two	2-4	2-4	20,000
7	Post-doctoral Research Certificate	One-Two	2-4	2-4	20,000

8. FACULTY RESEARCH EXPERTISE :

About 140 faculty members belonging to 8 Colleges of Srinivas University are actively involved in research and publications. From this year, each college/department of the University has planned 2 to 3 National conferences in emerging areas of their relevant subjects by involving students, researchers, and faculty members. Last year, the Srinivas Institute of Management Studies, the Social science, Business management, and Computer Applications wing of Srinivas University has grabbed 3rd Rank in Elsevier Publications SSRN Research network World Ranking based on Number of research papers published during last 12 months. Srinivas Institute of Management Studies also grabbed First Rank among International Business Schools other than USA under the category on number of Research papers Published during 12 months by Elsevier Publications SSRN Research network, USA.

Dr. P. S. Aithal, Vice Chancellor of Srinivas University has grabbed FIRST RANK among Top 12,000 Scholarly Business Authors of entire World 2018 based on number of research papers published during last one year by Elsevier’s SSRN Research network, USA. Table 3 contains the top ranks reached by Srinivas university faculty members during the year 2018.

Table 3 : Elsevier’s SSRN Top 1000 Business School Ranking based on number of Research papers published during the last 12 months, as on March, 2018

S. No.	Name of Business School & Country	Rank	No. of new Papers during last 12 months	Number of Registered Researchers
1	University of Pennsylvania – Wharton Business School, USA	01	270	448
2	UNSW Business School, Australia	02	255	362
3	Srinivas Institute of Management Studies, Srinivas University, India	03	237	52
4	New York University – Stern Business School, USA	04	222	357
5	University of Chicago – Booth Business School, USA	05	210	294
6	University of Virginia – Darden School of Business, USA	06	201	312
7	Columbia University – Columbia Business School	06	201	286
8	Harvard Business School – Harvard University, USA	08	174	360
9	MIT – Sloan School of Management, USA	09	166	267
10	Stanford Graduate School of Business, Stanford University, USA	10	126	176

Table 4 : Elsevier’s SSRN Ranking for Srinivas University Faculty members during June, 2018

S. No.	Name of Faculty members	Number of Publications during last 12 months (2017-18)	SSRN World Rank
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1	Dr. P. S. Aithal	121	01
2	Dr. Suresh Kumar	12	76
3	Dr. Laveena D'Mello	26	16
4	Dr. Krishna Prasad	17	42
5	Dr. Pradeep	10	71
6	Dr. Shubhrajyotsna Aithal	13	63
7	Prof. Shilashree	08	107
8	Prof. Preethi Jeevan	25	19
9	Prof. Varun Shenoy	13	34
10	Prof. Sridhar Acharya	12	62

Table 5 : Conferences & Research Papers Published by Srinivas University during last 3 years

S.No.	Research Based Activities during last 3 years	Quantity
1	National Conferences organized	18
2	Papers presented by Faculty members/ Students	1030
3	Papers published in conference Proceedings	560
4	Papers Published in Peer Reviewed Scholarly Journals	452
5	Books & Edited Books Published	52
6	Study Books prepared as per Curriculum	300+
7	Atomic Research Centres	225
8	Research Project Grants Received	2.5 Crores
9	Projects Applied	10 Crores

9. FUTURE INNOVATIONS OR UP-GRADATIONS TO ENHANCE EXISTING RESEARCH PROGRAMMES :

The following strategies are under implementation to upgrade and enhance existing research programmes :

- (1) Establishing the University Internal Research Fund to support researchers.
- (2) Collaborations with National & International universities.
- (3) Faculty Research Ranking & Incentives based on Annual Performance Indicator (API) Scores.
- (4) Empowering Atomic Research Centres of faculty members by allocating optimum resources.
- (5) Establishment of International Research centres in ICCT & Nanotechnology and expanding research areas under each centres.
- (6) Educating and encouraging students, researchers, & faculty members to apply for Patents.
- (7) Attracting more projects & funds from Industries and Government agencies.
- (8) Establishing National & International co-operation for collaborative research.

10. FUTURE ROADMAP SET FOR SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY TO REALIZE ITS GOALS :

The Srinivas University has created separate Centre for Research & Innovation, Technology-Business Incubator, and Entrepreneur Development Cells in its Colleges to enhance independent thinking & employability of its students and to support the start-ups with

expected funding from the Union Ministry of Small & Medium Enterprises, and the Department of IT, BT, and ST.

Srinivas University encourages its students to take part in International competitions, debates, sports, and other cultural events. With the slogan of “Your Career our Mission” Srinivas University is educating the next generation by investing its efforts to “Create Innovators to Serve the Society”. Equipped with state-of-the-art laboratory facilities, libraries, resource centres, and having implemented, proven, global academic educational practices, Srinivas University has set itself out to become a premier, Innovative, top Research University in international stature in the near future.

Srinivas University, based on its last few years research findings, identified two General purpose technologies called Information Communication & Computation technology (ICCT), and Nanotechnology (NT) as Universal technologies. These Universal Technologies can be used to solve all problems of the society related to Basic Needs, Advanced Wants, and Dreamy Desires of human beings. In future years Srinivas University is planned to focus its education and research activities on these two super-specialty areas of ICCT and NT by starting advanced research centers and UG, PG, and Research programmes to realize the future goal to become one of World Top Universities. As per the Chancellor Sri CA. A. Raghavendra Rao, the next three years will be crucial as we will introduce new colleges, departments and launching new programs. As Srinivas University gears towards realizing its goal of a research-led and skill-focused multi-disciplinary University, the commitment to create and disseminate knowledge is intrinsic of our journey. We have set our aim high and look forward to our journey and setting new milestones on the route which finally transforms society as integrated, harmonious, matured, developed, cultured, enjoyable and accountable for future generations.

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